

Book reviews

**Book Review: The dignity of a child as an anthropological-
pedagogical category [Godność dziecka jako kategoria
antropologiczno-pedagogiczna.] Warsaw, Maria Grzegorzewska
University Press [Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Akademii Pedagogiki
Specjalnej] by Wolman, Witold. 2021.**

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Abstract

Book review of Witold Wolman (2021). *The dignity of a child as an anthropological-pedagogical category*. Original Title: *Godność dziecka jako kategoria antropologiczno-pedagogiczna*.

Keywords

Child, Dignity, Equity, Subjectivity, Ethics, Anthropology, Education.

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The dignity of a child as an anthropological-pedagogical category is a Polish monograph by Wiktor Wolman, a doctor of social sciences, and an associate professor at the Faculty of Philosophy and Sociology of the Maria Grzegorzewska University.

The monograph includes thirteen chapters that make up five parts. It presents, or more precisely breaks down, in a multi-aspect manner, the issue of dignity, and not only that of children but human dignity in general.

Each of the book's five parts concerns a complete different perspective of dignity and issues strongly connected to it. The first part is devoted to the history of dignity. The author reaches back to the roots, bringing closer the issue and perception of dignity in antiquity, the Middle Ages, and modernity. He describes, defines, presents, and discusses it in a critical manner.

The second part constitutes a presentation of the concept of dignity from the perspective of four different and yet related sciences – philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy. The author not only presents the definitions, an image of the issue of dignity in a given field, but also makes an attempt to redefine the categories of dignity.

The following part refers to the real origins, foundations of the issue of dignity. The author brilliantly moves around international documents in which he finds a reflection of human dignity, as well as their equivalents on the Polish legal scene. In this chapter, the author also takes a closer look at children's rights as the overarching category of human rights, their history and the types of rights dedicated to children.

The following part of the monograph focuses strictly on the dignity of a child, in the form of considerations connecting the dignity of a child and the environment.

In this part, the author breaks down the family as a natural and initial environment of a child, as well as presents deliberations focusing on borderline situations and dilemmas concerning the dignity of a child.

As the author himself noted, instead of an ending, the final part constitutes a presentation of the ethical foundations of the dignity of a child. In this part the author discusses dignity in a broader context, taking into consideration the value of dignity, its neutrality, and in a way the necessity to have it.

As the author emphasizes "a child's nature is its dignity. A child comes into the world completely naked, in the literal and figurative sense of the word. It has no name, money, or position. The only thing it has is itself. It is a value in itself, and it gives value in itself" (Wolman, 2021).

An explicitly emphasized goal of the book consists in presenting the issue of dignity in a multi-aspect manner, as well attempting to redefine and identify the mechanisms that have an impact on the manner of perceiving, considering, as well as respecting the broadly understood human dignity, with special emphasis on the dignity of a child.

Despite the fact that the book includes deliberations of a clearly theoretical nature, it includes a compendium of knowledge concerning one of the biggest values of modern man, both adult and a child. Dr. Wolman's monograph constitutes a reflection on the changing world, passing time, and constant, natural values that guide human life.

The author of the monograph *The dignity of a child as an anthropological-pedagogical category* presents opinions, definitions, refers to legal knowledge used in practice, but primarily undertakes an attempt to convince the reader to reflect on the meaning and value of human dignity, with due diligence focusing the reader's attention on the dignity of a child. Doctor Wolman is not afraid to go into discussion with the reader, indicate contradictions, return to the roots of the issue, and consider it in a modern context.

The dignity of a child as an anthropological-pedagogical category by Wiktor Wolman is a book addressed to a wide audience of readers interested in an issue that is remarkably contemporary, especially in the context of the current situation in the world, but most importantly a subject important and close to every human being - adult or a child.